

DOUBOCHINSKI'S MACROCOHERENT PARADIGM (DMP)

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Summary

Doubochinski's Macrocoherent Paradigm (DMP) is a physical concept describing the emergence of stable collective regimes (macrocoherence) in ensembles of monochromatic classical oscillators interacting with monochromatic periodic excitation through argumental (frequency-phase) interaction.

The paradigm is based on experimental and theoretical studies of argumental oscillations and argumentale interactions, initiated by Danil and Yakov Doubochinski in the late 1960s, and demonstrates the possibility of realizing discrete stable regimes, system coherence, and self-organization in macroscopic classical systems without resorting to quantum postulates.

Key words ::pendulum, argumental interactions, phase modulation, multistability, coherence, resonance, frequency, self-organization, field, wave

Preface.

It is commonly believed that only quantum particles possess quantum coherence. Formally, says quantum mechanics - this property can be introduced also for classical macroscopic objects, but then one cannot do without paradoxes. One of them is, for example, Schrödinger's cat, which can be in superposition (i.e. simultaneously) of two states: it is both alive and dead. Quantum theory implies the existence of superposition states, which is justified by the linearity of Hilbert space. Presence of superposition in quantum theory, i.e. potential possession by a quantum object (for example, a particle) of several states, allows, for example, to use specially developed quantum algorithms for solving complex problems.

Theoretical and experimental studies of [15 - 27] argumental oscillatory processes and Macroscopic Quantum Effect, conducted by the authors of the discovery and confirmed by studies of scientists from many countries [72 - 103], showed that:

- at interaction of a macroscopic oscillatory system, (for example, a low-frequency oscillator) with an external periodic influence (force, wave or field) with different or equal natural frequencies, stable quasi-self-modes of oscillator oscillations at one of discrete amplitudes are possible. At unchanged parameters of two interacting vibrating objects, the number M ($M= 1, 2, 3, \dots$) of discrete stable states (modes) of the oscillator is determined by their frequency ratio and initial conditions. For example, at the frequency ratio $k = 20$, there can be 5 such states, and at $k = 100 \rightarrow M = 7$, etc;
- at interaction of two and more independent oscillatory systems with the same monochromatic energy source (wave, field, concentrated force) there takes place the unification of these systems, for example, oscillators into coherent structures (ensembles) with coordinated macroquantum states (see Fig. 6). This represents a previously unknown form of self-organization without direct interaction between oscillators;

** The paper uses fragments of articles written jointly with Dr. Jonathan Tennenbaum [8, 14, 21, 22, 28, 32], with whom the author has many years of joint work.

- it has been established that the new paradigm of argumental interactions is characterized not only by the presence of a force component, but also by the implementation of communication through the arguments of functions (phase, frequency, position), which provides flexibility and adaptability of these systems. This unites quantum, classical and self-organizing processes into a single theoretical paradigm.

The following results of our research are of particular interest.

The argumental oscillator possesses simultaneously two properties that distinguish it from its predecessor - the classical oscillator*, which has not yet entered the argumental interaction with an external periodic influence (wave, field, concentrated force).

When oscillating a classical monochromatic oscillator as a result of argumental interaction with an external periodic influence of a fixed frequency, the oscillator has a new property: it, in turn, influences the external influence and thus forms the conditions under which the exchange of energy and information between them provides resonant oscillator oscillations with a discrete series of stable amplitudes (see Appendix). That is, as a result of argumental interactions our classical oscillator has a macro-quantum duality: on the one hand, it is an oscillating mass (for example, a macroparticle), and on the other hand, it acts on the external influence as a kind of wave forming necessary and sufficient conditions for realization of stable quazi-own oscillations with a discrete series of quantized amplitudes (see Appendix).

In this context of macro-duality of behavior of a classical oscillator, participating in argumental interactions with an external periodic influence, one can represent macroquantum coherence similarly as it is formulated for quantum phenomena.

Macro-Quantum coherence is a macro-quantum phenomenon consisting in the coherence of motion of oscillators forming a given physical system. Macro-Quantum coherence is caused by macro-quantum duality of oscillators participating in argumental interactions. The presence of not only amplitude but also argumental components (phase, frequency, position) of the inverse impact of oscillators on the external periodic influence leads to the possibility of occurrence of macro-quantum coherence described by the concept of *macro-quantum state*. Such states of one and the same argumental (but, at the same time, classical) oscillator can have a discrete set n ($n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$).

Further, in the main part of the present paper the main properties and peculiarities of the mechanisms of excitation of argumental oscillations and interactions will be considered, which allowed us to formulate the main positions of macro-quantum coherence and connectedness of classical vibrational systems.

* **The basic property of a monochromatic classical oscillator excited by an external monochromatic influence is the one-way force coupling between them: the external force imposes on the oscillator the unambiguous possibility to have a solution at the frequency of the influence with an amplitude determined by the amplitude of the influence. Thus, in the classical case, the external force suppresses the oscillator's own behavior, depriving it of the possibility to exert a reciprocal influence on the influencing force.**

1. A phenomenological Model that preceded the discovery of argumantal oscillations

Let's assume that the oscillating electric charge intersects on its way a condensing interval, to which sinusoidal alternating voltage $F_0 \cos \Omega t$ is applied (Fig. 1). At the same time, we believe that the walls of the condenser are ideally permeable for the charge, the field inside the condenser is homogeneous and doesn't affect the oscillating charge outside the walls of the condenser [7, 9-13, 26].

Figure 1

Model experiment of the interaction of the charge with the field of capacitor gap

Let us further assume that the charge's transit time of the capacitor gap is infinitely small as compared to the oscillation period of the alternative field. In this case we can assume that the charge movement occurs during the constant (equal to instantaneous) value of the alternating field, that is, in essence, in the static field.

Lorsque les fréquences des oscillations naturelles de la charge et du champ alternatif sont incommensurables et que la probabilité de voler dans toutes les phases de ce champ alternatif est égale, il est évident que l'incrément total d'énergie pour un grand nombre d'oscillations de la charge sera égal à zéro.

If the charge's transit time of the capacitor gap is finite, that is can be compared with the period of alternative voltage, then the field, in which the charge moves, cannot be considered static, as during the time that the charge transits the field, the latter changes. However, for the case, when the transit time of the capacitor gap is equal to the period of oscillations of the alternative field, you cannot expect any changes in energy balance of charge's oscillations, as in this case as well, the average value of energy input during the period when the charges stays in the capacitor gap will be zero (the charge accelerates during the first half of the period, and decelerates during the second half of the period).

We faced the question: whether, with incommensurability of frequencies of charge's proper oscillations and alternative voltage (for the case with the finite transit time of the interaction zone) energy input of the alternating field into the charge's oscillations is possible and what are the conditions for reproducing such oscillating processes?

Let us consider the case when the undisturbed transit time $\tau \approx \frac{3}{4}T$ (T is the period of alternating field) and the field in the capacitor gap is very weak. For such case depending on the phase of charge entry into the capacitor gap, it will be influenced by forces different in magnitude and direction.

Let us assume that the initial entry phase is zero ($\varphi = 0$). Then during the first half of the period the charge will be accelerated by the field, and during the next quarter of the period – will be decelerated. As the result of single span with such initial phase we observe dominating acceleration of the charge by the field.

If the entry is made with the phase $\varphi = \pi$, during the first half of the period the field will decelerate the charge, and during the next quarter of the period – accelerate it. As the result of single-span entry with this initial phase, we have the dominating charge deceleration.

If the transit time of the charge of the condensing interval does not change, then the values of energy input in both cases discussed above will be identical and opposite. The similar relation of energy input will be observed if we consider any pairs of initial entry phases φ and $\varphi + \pi$. Therefore, with the unchanged transit time $\tau = \tau_0$, then total energy contribution in a greater number of oscillations will be zero.

Let us consider the case when the amplitude of the field of the capacitor gap is quite large for a light charge to change its actual time of movement in the capacitor gap (Fig. 2).

In this case with the initial phase $\varphi_1 = 0$ the actual transit time τ_1 will be less than unexcited transit time $\tau \approx \frac{3}{4}T$. Thus, energy contribution into charge oscillations will be less than the contribution, which occurred at the corresponding constant transit time τ_0 . The positive energy contribution for this case is proportional to the shaded area at Fig. 2, a with the “plus” sign.

Figure 2

“Energy-phase” diagrams for the interaction model of charge with alternating field of the capacitor gap

With the initial phase $\varphi_2 = \pi$ the actual transit time τ_2 increases by comparison with $\varphi_1 = 0$, which effects in lesser deceleration of the charge by the field (Fig. 2,b). Energy contribution in this case will be proportional to the shaded area at Fig. 2,b with the “minus” sign.

Comparison of energy ratios for the considered pair of entry phase, leads to the conclusion about the resulting positive energy contribution for a larger number of oscillations of the charge (see Fig. 2,c). Similarly, we can argue about any other two, taken in pairs, spans with the initial phases φ and $\varphi + \pi$ (see, for example, Fig. 2 d, e).

Therefore, we can confirm that with incommensurable frequency of the oscillation system and a variable of external force, positive energy contribution can occur only under the condition that the system changes the spans time through the interaction zone.

We can repeat similar arguments for the case of rotational motion of the charge on non-stretchable thread around a fixed point. In this case, if the resulting energy contribution of the alternating field will compensate for the loss of energy due to friction, to the real time of interaction of the charge with the field will correspond to the stable regime of charge rotations.

It is quite obvious that the specified model representations are also valid in the case where the initial conditions are set, for example, by the ratio of

$$\tau_n = T(n + \tau) \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots).$$

In the case where $\tau \approx \frac{3}{4}T$, each value of n (where $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$) will correspond to the stable modes of oscillations (or rotations) of the pendulum. Therefore, in such system we should expect possible excitation of oscillations with a discrete series n of stable amplitudes.

Studies carried out by the authors of MQED showed [7, 9 – 10, 13], that on average for one half-period of oscillations, the pendulum will receive positive energy supplement in the zone of interaction with external harmonic force.

The results received are not fundamentally new from the standpoint of processes that take place during the interaction of charged particles flows with alternating field of capacitor gap in microwave electronic devices. However, their recovery for one-particle task allowed to take the next step which is the transition from model, purely qualitative reasoning to real macrophysical models.

The macrophysical analog of the considered interactions of charge with the alternating field of the capacitor gap is, for example, the interaction of a permanent magnet, which is part of a physical pendulum, with the alternating field of a solenoid (see Fig. 1.3). The system in FIG. 1.3, is a pendulum with a permanent magnet 1, the poles of which are arranged perpendicular to a non-stretchable pendulum string 2. The upper end of the non-stretchable thread 2 is fixed in the suspension system 3-5 rigidly connected with the frame 6, 8. The natural frequency of small free oscillations of the pendulum is close to 0.5 Hz, the idle goodness is close to 50.

Symmetrically to pendulum equilibrium position on the base stand 6 two identical solenoids 7 are preset, which are powered from AC 50 Hz circuit through speed changer, which allows adjusting the amplitude voltage (current) on solenoids 7 within the range of 15 to 250 V. The design peculiarities of the model presented in Fig. 3, allow to practically limit the interaction zone of permanent magnet 1 with alternating field of solenoids 7 with size d , which characterizes the length of solenoid coil block. Provision is also made for varying the amplitude and frequency parameters of the power supply to the solenoids 7.

It is obvious that the real macrophysical model presented in Fig. 3 is similar to the model of charge interaction with alternating field of capacitor gap (see Fig. 1).

The studies carried out on the installation (see Fig. 3) showed, that when the pendulum starts with the initial conditions that correspond to the amplitudes (counted from the equilibrium position) 45°, 60°, 74°, 80° and 90°, and the solenoids 7 voltage equal to 30 V, stable oscillations of the pendulum take place for all fixed pendulum parameters values 1-2 and power supply.

- Designations**
- 1 - Permanent magnet,
 - 2 - Rigid rod,
 - 3, 4, 5 - Bearing suspension of the pendulum,
 - 6, 8 - Base of the device,
 - 7 - Inductive coil
 - d - length of inductive coil (interaction zone)

Figure 3

The interaction model of physical pendulum with solenoid

Thus, it was experimentally established that in real macrophysically system the realization of interaction principles is possible, which was earlier considered acceptable only for acceleration (braking) of micro-physical objects – charged particles.

2. Argumental interactions and the Macroscopic Quantum Effect

The Macroscopic Quantum Effect (MQE) arises when two or more oscillating systems, having widely differing frequencies, become coupled to each other by interactions having a specific phase dependent character -- so-called argumental interactions. Ensembles of argumentally interacting macroscopic oscillators possess a discrete set of stable quasi-stationary modes and other characteristics strikingly similar to microscopic quantum physical objects. The theory and experimental justification of the MQED have been developed and presented in the scientific literature [2, 3]. For the present purposes, we review the main features of the argumental oscillator, which is a classic experimental demonstration of MQED, and then extend them to argument-interacting systems in general.

2.1. The argumental oscillator

2.1.1. Argumental pendulum of Doubochinski [27, 30, 50, 68 – 75]

The argumental pendulum (Fig. 4) is composed of two interacting oscillatory systems : (1) a mechanical pendulum with a natural frequency on the order of 1-2 Hz, with a small permanent magnet fixed at its moving end; and (2) a stationary electromagnet (solenoid) positioned under the equilibrium point of the pendulum's trajectory and supplied with alternating current whose frequency can range from tens to thousands of hertz. The pendulum and solenoid are configured in such a way, that the pendulum interacts with the oscillating magnetic field of the solenoid only over a limited portion of its trajectory. This spatial heterogeneity of the interaction allows the pendulum to self-regulate its exchange of energy with the magnetic field.

Released from any given position, the pendulum's motion evolves into a stable, very nearly periodic motion whose amplitude takes one of a discrete array of possible values (Fig. 5). The stability of each amplitude is maintained by a constant adjustment (via fluctuations) of the phase relationship between the pendulum and the high-frequency field. Through its interaction with the field over a given period of oscillation, the pendulum extracts an amount of energy exactly sufficient, on average, to compensate its frictional losses for the same period. The values of the quantized amplitudes -- and the corresponding energies of the quantized modes -- are essentially independent of the strength of the alternating current supplied to the electromagnet, over a very large range [29].

Figure 4.

Argumental pendulum

Figure 5

First four stable discrete amplitudes of oscillations of the argumental pendulum

The maintenance of these quantized amplitudes depends upon a new mechanism of exchange of energy between oscillating systems, differing fundamentally from the mechanisms studied in the classical theory of oscillations, in particular the familiar case of "forced oscillations" of an oscillator under the action of a periodic external force. In the classical case, a significant exchange of energy between the oscillator and the external signal occurs only when the frequency of the external force is very close to the proper frequency of the oscillator. In the case of the argumental pendulum, by contrast, the frequency of the magnetic field, from which the pendulum extracts the energy necessary to maintain its undamped motion, can be two or more orders of magnitude higher than that of the pendulum itself. The latter is close to the proper frequency of the undisturbed pendulum.

The ability of argumental interactions to efficiently convert oscillatory energy over such a wide range of frequencies differences is inseparably connected with the role of fluctuations and self-regulating behavior [49, 56, 64].

In the classical (Newtonian) mode of interaction, a system being acted upon by an external force is virtually the "slave" of that force; the Newtonian concept of force leaves no room for a true mutual interaction and mutual adaptation of the interacting systems to each other. The argumental pendulum, by contrast, remains "its own master": By shifting the phase of entry into the interaction zone, it can self-regulate its exchange of energy with the electromagnet.

Careful observation and reflection on the behavior of the argumental pendulum results in a number of conclusions of fundamental importance.

Firstly, each stable, quasi-periodic mode (amplitude) of the pendulum, resulting from the interaction of the pendulum and the magnetic field, constitutes an oscillating system in its own right, with its own distinct energetic and other physical parameters. In such a situation, we can speak of the simultaneous existence of no less than three oscillating systems:

System A - the classical oscillator formed by the pendulum interacting with the gravitational field of the Earth;

System B - the electromagnet (considered together with its alternating current power source),

System C - the compound oscillating system constituted from the interaction of A and B at any of the stable amplitudes.

It is extremely important to note that during the interaction forming system C, the physical parameters of systems A and B change only slightly; each of them retains its "identity" and integrity as an oscillating system. Thus, the pendulum (system A) continues to make its own periodic motions under the action of gravity, simultaneously experiencing the effects (oscillations of amplitude and phase) due to the action of the electromagnetic field. The system of the electromagnet and its current source (system B) maintains its basic frequency and amplitude characteristics, while experiencing periodic influences due to the currents induced by the movement of the permanent magnet of the pendulum through the interaction zone.

The fact, that the two coupled systems A and B retain their essential integrity in the compound system, expresses a very special property of the mechanism of argumental interactions, which distinguishes it fundamentally from the much more rigid classical (and also quantum-mechanical) forms of coupling. In the latter cases, the parameters of the compound systems are not only drastically modified, but the subsystems lose their independence entirely, "melting" into a single combined system with (generally speaking) entirely different parameters.

Secondly, as already pointed out, the stable functioning of the coupled system, in a given mode, depends upon the role phase fluctuations. Thus, in place of the rigid, "dead" form of Newtonian coupling, argumental interactions have the living, dynamic character which we justifiably attribute to true physical objects.

The above considerations lead to an interesting and rather peculiar form of "arithmetic".

In the classical theory of oscillating systems, the coupling of two oscillators produces a new system – a result we might describe, in symbolic form, as follows:

$$A + B = C.$$

Note, that in this classical sort of rigid coupling, the systems A and B lose their independence entirely and as such cease to exist as individual entities; now only the system C exists.

In the case of the argumentally coupling of oscillators, however, the component systems A and B maintain a certain degree of independence and retain very nearly their previous, characteristic oscillatory parameters within the compound system. Hence the result is 3 systems, rather than just one as in the classical case. We might write this as follows:

$$A + B = \{ A, B, C \} \quad (1)$$

We should not forget, however, that the argumental coupling between A and B, upon which the integrity and stability of the third system C depends, also constitutes a physical object in its own right. Accordingly, it will be more correct to write:

$$A + B = \{ A, B, C, K \} \quad (2)$$

where K denotes the argumental coupling.

In actuality, argumentally coupled oscillators such as argumental pendulums generally possess not just one, but an entire discrete array of quantized stable modes. Each of these, when realized, constitutes a distinct physical entity with its own characteristic parameters, and each of these is "virtually" present, as a potentiality, in any given coupled state of A and B. We might therefore write, more correctly:

$$A + B = \{ A, B, \{C_n, K_n\}_{n=1,2,3\dots N} \}$$

or

$$A + B = \{ A, B, (AB)_n \}, \quad (3)$$

where $(AB)_n$ represents one of the discrete states of the coupled system.

Later in this article (see § 2.4) we will further expand on this "non-linear arithmetic" which we believe may be related to the mechanisms of development in Nature.

The immensity of possibilities of generation of new physical entities (systems, structures and their states), realized already at the level of argument interaction of only two constituents, is most clearly manifested if we consider more complex argumental formations (see § 2.4 [18, 24, 25, 38, 47, 51]).

2.1.2. Interaction modeling

It corresponds to the case reflected on Figure 4, when external force can be represented with the following equation:

$$\Phi(x, t) = A\varepsilon(x) \sin(\Omega t), \quad (4)$$

where $\varepsilon(x)$ is the function, which characterizes the non-uniformity of the force along the X-axis of the pendulum's motion (see Figure 4) and can be presented as follows:

$$\varepsilon(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } |x| \leq X_0 \\ 0, & \text{if } |x| > X_0. \end{cases} \quad (4')$$

Then the motion equation, which describes the oscillations in the system on Figure 4, can be presented as follows:

$$\ddot{x} + 2\beta \dot{x} + \omega_0^2 x + f(x) = \Phi(x, t) = A\varepsilon(x) \sin(\Omega t). \quad (5)$$

Let us consider the case when the solution of the equation (5) takes the form:

$$x = a \sin \theta, \quad \theta = \omega_0 t + \alpha, \quad a = a(t), \quad \alpha = \alpha(t), \quad (5')$$

assuming that

$$\dot{x} = a\omega \cos \theta \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{a} \sin \theta + a\dot{\alpha} \cos \theta = 0. \quad (5'')$$

Let us expand the function (4') in a Fourier's series:

$$\varepsilon(a \sin \theta) = C_0(a) + 2 \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} C_{2m}(a) \cos 2m\theta, \quad (6)$$

where

$$C_{2m}(a) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \varepsilon(a \sin \theta) \cos 2m\theta d\theta \quad (6')$$

Taking into account (6) we find the following expression for function $\Phi(x,t)$:

$$\varepsilon(a \sin \theta) \sin \Omega t = C_0(a) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} C_{2m} [\sin(\Omega t - 2m\theta) + \sin(\Omega t + 2m\theta)]. \quad (7)$$

The second summand in the right part of the equation (7) has the form, which is identical to the representation in radiophysics of a signal modulated by frequency and/or phase. The segment of the possible frequency spectrum, which was received as the result of external force modulation (4) by the oscillator, which has its natural frequency ω_0 , is shown on Figure 6.

Such mode of combined behavior of the systems (see (5)), as the result of which the pendulum realizes the modulation of external force and expands it in a series (7), which contains the frequency spectrum $\Omega \pm n\omega_0$ (see for example Figure 6), we will call *argumental interactions*.

Figure 6

Fragment of the spectrum of possible frequencies

Also, as during frequency-phase modulation of signals in radiophysics, the received frequency spectra during argumental interaction of systems are not restricted by a certain number of components. Therefore, if as the result of the interaction of the external periodic force (4) with the pendulum (stt Fig. 4) the following condition is met:

$$\Omega \pm n\omega_0 = |\omega_0| \quad (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots), \quad (1)$$

then in the system, represented by the equation (3') stationary modes of pendulum's can be excited at the frequency close to its natural frequency ω_0 . This result is reliably confirmed by the experimental researches [8, 9, 26, 29] described in the previous sections of the current monograph.

Thus, the contribution of the energy of the external periodic force (4) to the natural (or close to them) motions of the mechanical pendulum, necessary to compensate its frictional energy losses and to maintain stationary oscillation amplitudes, can be realized by frequency-phase modulation by the pendulum of the mode of operation of the external force with which it interacts

Such mechanism of energy conversion was not previously addressed to by the classical physics and mechanics. The main peculiarity of this mechanism is the fact that the energy transformation occurs due to the interaction of initial systems, and in terms of classical theory – due to the effect of the oscillator on the frequency and/or phase of external action. In the terms of equation (7) it means that the pendulum affects *the argument* of external force, destined to provide energy input into its oscillations.

It is vital to understand the manner in which stationary modes of the researched object (pendulum, oscillator) are realized during argumental interactions. This is an absolutely unconventional mechanism of selective-phase character, the physical essence of which is researched in the next sections of the given paper.

Method for Calculating Quantized Discrete Amplitudes

Taking into account (5') and (5'') we form \dot{x} and \ddot{x} and, substituting these values into the equation (5) we get the following equation system:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{a} = \frac{\omega_0^2 - \omega^2}{\omega} a \sin \theta \cos \theta + \frac{1}{\omega} f(a \sin \theta, \omega a \cos \theta) \cos \theta + \frac{A}{\omega} \varepsilon(a \sin \theta) \cos \theta \sin \Omega t, \\ \dot{\alpha} = \frac{\omega_0^2 - \omega^2}{\omega} \sin^2 \theta - \frac{1}{a\omega} f(a \sin \theta, \omega a \cos \theta) \sin \theta - \frac{A}{a\omega} \varepsilon(a \sin \theta) \sin \theta \sin \Omega t, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

and we will apply averaging process to it [39].

Under the condition

$$\Omega \approx n\omega, \quad n = 2m + 1 \quad (\text{where } n \text{ is an odd number}) \quad \text{and} \quad \omega \approx \omega_0 \quad (9)$$

then the averaged equations (8) will look as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{a} = -\frac{\beta}{2} + \frac{A}{2\omega} (C_{n-1} + C_{n+1}) \sin \varphi \\ \dot{\varphi} = \Omega - n\omega - n \left[\frac{\omega^2 - \omega_a^2}{2\omega} - \frac{A}{2a\omega} (C_{n-1} - C_{n+1}) \cos \varphi \right], \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\varphi = \Omega t - n\theta = (\Omega - n\omega)t - n\alpha, \quad (11)$$

$$\dot{\varphi} = \Omega - n(\omega + \dot{\alpha}), \quad (12)$$

$$\omega_a^2 = \frac{2J_1(a)}{a} \omega_0^2 \approx \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{8} + \dots\right) \omega_0^2, \quad (13)$$

ω_a is the frequency of free oscillations of the mechanical pendulum with the finite amplitude a (it is defined by the averaging process [39] with $A=0$ and $\beta=0$), $J_1(a)$ is Bessel function of the first kind.

In correspondence with the correlation (9) and in correspondence with the results of experimental researches [7] we suggest that:

$$\omega_n = \Omega / n. \quad (14)$$

Then for stationary oscillations of a mechanical oscillator, and taking into account (14), the correlation (13), in a first approximation, can be represented as follows:

$$(\Omega/n)^2 = \omega_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{a_n^2}{8}\right) \quad (14')$$

So, the correlations (14') defines the relationship between the discrete (quantized) values of the stationary amplitudes of the oscillator oscillations a_n and the frequency Ω of the external force, which to a sufficient degree of approximation [7, 29] can be represented by the following correlation:

$$a_n \approx \sqrt{8\left(1 - \frac{\Omega}{n\omega_0}\right)^2} \approx 4\sqrt{1 - \frac{\Omega}{n\omega_0}} \approx 4\sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega_n}{\omega_0}}. \quad (15)$$

where

$$n = 2m + \kappa, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad \kappa = 1, 3, 5, \dots, \quad \omega = 2\pi f,$$

f is the actual frequency of the oscillator oscillations.

Figure 7 shows the resonance characteristic of the oscillation mode of an undisturbed oscillator (solid line), built by using the formula:

$$\omega^2 = \omega_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{8}\right). \quad (16)$$

Let us consider the algorithm for defining stationary quantized discrete amplitudes of oscillator oscillations with some fixed parameters of mechanical pendulum (in general case, oscillator) shown on Figure 4 ($\omega_0=2\pi f_0$, $f_0=0.5\text{Hz}$) and various values of frequencies $\Omega = 2\pi f_\Omega$ of the external force.

Let us assume that oscillator frequency is $f_0=0.5$ Hz and force frequency is $f_\Omega=5$ Hz, in other words $\Omega/\omega_0 = 2\pi f_\Omega / 2\pi f_0 = 10$. Then, according to the correlation $n=2m+k$ (see correlations (15)), then only one spectral component of the external force modulated by the oscillator (with which the oscillator interacts) will hit the region of undisturbed resonance characteristic (16) of the oscillator. It corresponds to the eleventh multiplicity n of frequencies Ω and ω . On Figure 7 the coordinates of this spectral component are marked with a dashed line. It means that with all values of multiplicity of frequencies $n=\Omega/\omega_n=2m+k$, for which $m \leq 5$, stable oscillations of the oscillator can be realized with one stationary amplitude, for which $k=1$.

If $f_\Omega=20$ Hz ($2m = \Omega/\omega_0 = 2\pi f_\Omega / 2\pi f_0 = 40$) then according to (15), four spectral components of the external force modulated by the oscillator will hit the region of resonance characteristic (16) and they will correspond to 41st, 43rd, 45th, and 47th multiplicities of $n = \Omega/\omega_n = 2m + \kappa$ ($m = 0, 1, 2, \dots; \kappa=1,3,5,7,\dots$) frequencies. This case is shown on Fig. 8. The following values of spectral components of frequency $\Omega/n=\omega_n$ and discrete stationary amplitudes (15) of oscillator oscillations a_n [29]:

$$\omega_{41} = \Omega/41 = 3,06 \text{ rad/s}, \quad \omega_{43} = \Omega/43 = 2,92 \text{ rad/s}, \quad \omega_{45} = \Omega/45 = 2,79 \text{ rad/s},$$

$$\omega_{47} = \Omega/47 = 2,68 \text{ rad/s}; \quad a_{41} = 35,6^\circ, \quad a_{43} = 59,5^\circ, \quad a_{45} = 74,2^\circ, \quad a_{47} = 85^\circ.$$

Fig. 7

Resonance characteristic of pendulum

Fig. 8

Spectral characteristic of external force

That is why to define quantized discrete amplitudes of stationary oscillations of the oscillator, which can be realized only under specific values of oscillator and external force parameters, it is necessary to involve the mechanism of stability theory.

The main principles of the research of argumental oscillations stability are covered in monographs [7,29].

To evaluate the efficiency of applying the method for calculating quantized discrete amplitudes of stationary oscillations of argument oscillator, described above, we provided the data of experimental research in Table 2 alongside the calculation data, obtained according to the equations (14) and (15). The data of experimental research we obtained on a specially created installation [7]. Table 2 also contains the results of numerical experiment performed on computer, when we examined equation (5) with the following values of its parameters:

$$2\beta=0,01, \quad \omega_0 = 3,14 \text{ rad/s}, \quad A = 10 \text{ V}, \quad X_0=0,012 \text{ m}, \quad F = 50 \text{ Hz}, \quad \Omega = 314 \text{ rad/s}. \quad (17)$$

The comparison of the results, we obtained in various ways, (see Table 2) allows us to make a conclusion that the suggested algorithm (14)-(15) for calculating discrete quantized amplitudes of oscillator's stationary oscillations provides sufficient approximation to the data of experimental research and can be used for creating argument oscillatory systems.

Let us go back to equations (10) - (14).

These equations are applicable both for analysis of stationary oscillations and analysis of the processes of their settlement. They define the connection between values of the amplitude A of the external force and amplitude a of oscillator oscillations in stationary mode.

The following conditions correspond to stationary oscillator oscillations:

$$\dot{a} = 0, \quad \dot{\alpha} = 0, \quad \dot{\varphi} = 0,$$

$$\omega_n + \dot{\alpha}_n = \frac{\Omega}{n},$$

this means that the frequency ω_n is the odd spectral component of the frequency Ω of the external force.

With the suggestion made earlier for the correlation of frequencies Ω and ω ($\omega_n = \Omega/n$), in stationary mode of the oscillator the equation system (10) can be represented as:

$$\begin{aligned} A \sin \varphi &= \frac{\omega_0^2 a \delta_0}{C_{n-1} + C_{n+1}}, & \delta_0 &= \frac{2\beta\omega}{\omega_0^2}, \\ A \cos \varphi &= \frac{\omega_0^2 a \delta_0}{C_{n-1} - C_{n+1}}, & \delta &= \frac{\omega^2 - \omega_a^2}{\omega_0^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

which define amplitude α and phase $\varphi = -\pi\alpha$ of oscillator's stationary oscillations [29].

Table 2

n = Ω/ω frequency ratio	101	103	105	107	109	111	113	115	117
a_n amplitudes of pendulum's oscillations received by calculations according to the suggested algorithm (14)-(15) (in degrees)	22,8	39,1	50,0	58,6	65,9	72,1	77,3	82,8	87,4
a_n amplitudes of pendulum's oscillations received on the installation shown on Figure 4 (in degrees)	30,0	43,2	53,2	59,9	68,0	74,2	79,8	84,9	89,3
a_n amplitudes of pendulum's oscillations received during numerical experiment of equation (3') on computer under the conditions (17) (in degrees)	29,6	43,3	53,4	60,1	68,4	74,5	80,0	84,9	89,4

Note: The conformance of the results of calculations according to the suggested algorithm (14)-(15) and experimental research can be evaluated by the ratio of the corresponding values of a_n of the first and second rows of Table 2, for which the deviation from each other, starting from $n=105$, does not exceed 7%.

From (18) we can define the relationship between amplitudes \mathbf{A} and α by means of simple transformations. It looks as follows:

$$A = \omega_0^2 a \sqrt{\left(\frac{\delta_0}{C_{n-1} + C_{n+1}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta}{C_{n-1} - C_{n+1}}\right)^2}. \quad (19)$$

By inserting function (4') into integral (6'), we obtain:

$$C_n = \frac{2 \sin n\theta}{\pi n}, \quad \theta = \arcsin \frac{x_0}{a} \approx \frac{x_0}{a} \quad \text{with} \quad \frac{x_0}{a} \ll 1$$

and the stationarity properties of oscillator's oscillations result from the following conditions:

- 1) with $\theta_0 \ll 1$ and $n\theta_0 \geq 1$ the coefficients C_{n-1} and C_{n+1} differ little from each other, that is why in correlations (18) and (19) their diminution is significantly less than the total;
- 2) the value δ in correlations (18) and (19) depends on amplitude α , in consequence of formulas (11) and (12) we have:

$$\delta \approx \frac{a^2 - a_0^2}{8} \approx \frac{a_0}{4} (a - a_0), \quad a_0 \approx 4 \sqrt{8 \left(1 - \frac{\omega}{\omega_0^2}\right)^2}.$$

That is why with greater values of A the dependence A from α will be practically linear:

$$A = \frac{\omega_0^2 a_0}{4} \frac{(a - a_0)}{|C_{n-1}(a_0) - C_{n+1}(a_0)|}. \quad (20)$$

Formula (20) implies that if we increase A by 15 times, amplitude will change less than by 0.3%.

The aforementioned results of researches allow us to arrive at the conclusion that the oscillations frequency of the oscillator and the energy consumed by it practically are not affected by the changes of intensity of the external periodic force in the wide range.

Table 3 shows the result of a numerical experiment on a computer: we investigated differential equation (3') for the case when the amplitude of external force, interacting with the oscillator, changed within the range from 2V to 30V with fixed values of all other parameters (17). The experiment was carried out with the fixed initial conditions of oscillator's launch, which allowed it to oscillate with the amplitude $a_{103} \approx 43^0 \approx 0,75$ rad.

The values presented in table 3 are grouped into the following order:

- 1st row - specified values of amplitude \mathbf{A} of external force, in V
- 2nd row - values of amplitude α_{103} of oscillator oscillations, in radians
- 3rd row - values of energy \mathbf{E} , received by the oscillator in the zone $[-X_0, X_0]$ as the result of interaction with external force (see Figure 4), in Joules
- 4th and 5th rows - values of phase ψ_1 and ψ_2 of oscillations correspondingly at the moments when oscillator entered and left the interaction zone $[-X_0, X_0]$ (see Figure 4), in radians.

Table 4, by analogy with Table 3, contains data of research for the case when coefficient 2β in equation (5), which characterizes oscillator's dissipative energy losses, accepts various positive, zero or negative values (first column in the table). All other conditions of the experiment are identical to the ones accepted for the case presented in Table 3. The value of amplitude $A = 15V$ remained unchanged for all variants of values of coefficient 2β .

As you can see from the table 3, the change in amplitude A of external force by 15 times practically didn't lead to changes of the energy consumed by the oscillator (see column 3). The experiment also proved that there are minimal (threshold) values of amplitude of the external force ($A = 2V$) and energy ($E = 0.027$ Joules), below which oscillator's argumental oscillations are not excited.

Figure 9
Energy Self-regulation

Table 3

A	a_{103}	E	ψ_1	ψ_2
2	0,7545	0,0270	0,1088	1,1381
3	0,7547	0,0269	0,2757	1,3043
5	0,7548	0,0269	0,3670	1,3919
10	0,7553	0,0269	0,4311	1,4498
15	0,7557	0,0270	0,4529	1,4680
30	0,7571	0,0270	0,4697	1,4803

Table 4

2β	a_{103}	E	ψ_1	ψ_2
0,075	0,7542	0,2016	0,1077	1,1361
0,025	0,7551	0,0672	0,3849	1,3079
0,0075	0,7558	0,0202	0,3629	1,3628
0,0010	0,7558	0,0027	0,4552	1,4678
0,0	0,7558	0,0	0,4848	1,5036
-0,050	0,7558	-0,1344	0,6981	1,6071

The research data in Table 4 allow us to make the following conclusions. Stationary argument oscillations of oscillator (see column 2 - the values of amplitude α_{103}) are realized only when its quality factor changes (see coefficient 2β - column 1) in the wide range. At the same time, the energy amount, consumed by the oscillator, is determined by its quality factor $Q = \omega / 2\beta$ and amplitude α_n ($n=1,2,3,\dots$) of its oscillations.

It must be particularly noted that for the first time ever it was theoretically and experimentally proved that stationary oscillations do exist when external periodic force interacts with a conservative oscillator, i.e. when $2\beta = 0$ (see row 5 in table 4).

We obtained similar results in the cases when external periodic force interacted with linear and quasi-linear oscillators.

2.1.3. Energy Self-regulation

The carried out theoretical, experimental, and numerical research allowed us to study the main characteristics of the energy self-regulation mechanism when amplitude \mathbf{A} of the external periodic force were changing. The first three values of amplitude \mathbf{A} were considered, from those shown in Table 3.

The physical meaning of the energy self-regulations mechanism consists of the following.

In accordance with charts on Figure 9, the energy consumed by the pendulum, consists of two parts, the first one accelerates it (marked in the chart with \oplus sign), and the second one brakes it (marked with \ominus sign). The resulting energy, consumed by the oscillator, is characterized by the area, which is shaded simultaneously in both directions. It is also obvious that all energy packets, shown on these charts, are univalently determined by the values of entering phase ψ_1 and exiting phase ψ_2 of the zone $[-X_0, X_0]$ of oscillator's interaction with external periodic force (see Figure 4).

The fulfillment of the consistency condition, in average, of energy packet (macroquantum) when changing the intensity of external periodic interaction, with which the oscillator interacts, is provided by the autophasing mechanism. It is based on automatic shifting (transition) of phase ψ_1 (see Table 3, column 4) to the region of such values, at which we observe the compensation of the energy 'surplus', which is supplied to the oscillator by the external force as the result of their interaction. On average, the multiplicity \mathbf{n} of frequency oscillations of the oscillator ω and external influence Ω , and amplitude α_n ($n=1,2,3,..$) of oscillator's oscillations are kept steadily constant.

As in the case of changing the intensity of external periodic influence, with which the oscillator interacts, the autophasing mechanism regulates energy processes when there are changes in oscillator's dissipativity β (quality factor Q) in the wide range (see Table 4). Les amplitudes d'oscillation de l'oscillateur en régime permanent α_n ($n=1,2,3,..$) sont réalisées régulièrement, en moyenne.

With $\beta = 0$ (conservative oscillator) phase ψ_1 (see Table 4, column 4) shifts to such range of values, at which the energy, which accelerates the oscillator, is fully compensated by its braking energy. That is why the resulting input of the external periodic influence on oscillator's oscillations equals zero.

We also proved that similar results of excitation of argumental oscillations with a discrete range of discrete quantized amplitudes of stationary oscillations can be also observed in cases when the frequency of the external periodic influence differs from oscillator's frequency by hundred or thousand times.

2.2. Stochastic (chaotic) Oscillator [71]

The Doubochinski's stochastic oscillator is a classical mechanical pendulum that, when interacting with a high-frequency field, implements undamped chaotic oscillations with a frequency close (on average) to the natural frequency of the oscillator. This system is based on the principles of interaction that underlie the basic argumental-coupled oscillator considered above in § 2.1.

The difference between the two pendulums is that in the basic argumental-coupled pendulum its moving part is made of hard material, and in the stochastic (chaotic) pendulum it is made of elastic material, for example, of thin elastic wire or string. In this case, the mechanical oscillator is a system with two degrees of freedom.

It is also possible to implement stochastic regimes when the mechanical part of the system does not differ from the basic oscillator see (Fig. 4 and [30, 71]). In this case, the pendulum makes periodic motions with multiple transitions to different stable amplitudes, and circular motions transforming into oscillations are also possible.

It was experimentally established that after a certain period of time of system's operation, stochastic oscillations of an oscillator with two degrees of freedom begin to correlate. Thus, the pendulum begins to oscillate with an amplitude close, on average, to one of the stable amplitudes. This example illustrates the possibility of a transition from chaotic behavior to the correlation regime of periodic motions for the case when oscillatory systems realize argumental interactions.

2.3. A system of multiple argumental interactions

Figure 10 shows a schematic diagram of a device consisting of four argumental pendulums (discussed in § 2.1) with different natural frequencies. These pendulums are capable of realizing undamped quasi natural oscillations by interacting with the high-frequency field of the same inductive coil fed from an AC source, e.g., 50 Hz.

This device demonstrates the phenomenon of effective resonant transformation of the energy of the same energy source (in this case represented by a solenoid, which is connected to the AC network of monochromatic frequency) into the energy of periodic motions of mechanical oscillating systems with different natural frequencies.

Our studies have shown a number of new and important results for comprehension. For example, we studied the oscillations of four pendulums with natural frequencies of ~0.3 Hz, ~0.5 Hz, ~0.7 Hz, and ~1 Hz, which were reproduced at quasi natural frequencies in the range from 0° to 90°. In the experiment, independent oscillations of each of the pendulums with 3, 5, 6, and 8 steady amplitudes, respectively, were realized in the argument interaction mode with the same electromagnet connected directly to a 50 Hz AC network.

With four pendulums swinging simultaneously, it was possible to realize 2 stable amplitudes for the first pendulum, 4 stable amplitudes for the second pendulum, 5 stable amplitudes for the third pendulum, and 6 stable amplitudes for the fourth pendulum.

Thus, it has been shown that argumental interactions and multiple resonance can be realized when the frequencies of the systems differ from each other and from the energy source by tens and hundreds of times [32, 54].

Figure 10

Four low-frequency argumental pendulums, interacting with the magnet field of one and the same inductive coil, supplied by high-frequency AC source

The system stability of complex formations of oscillatory systems is thus ensured by adapting oscillators to each other by regulating the number of possible stable multi-resonance modes of individual systems.

Thus, the interrelation of oscillators among themselves, consisting in the regulation of possible stable combinations (states) of their stable dynamic modes, was fixed.

This example demonstrates the peculiarities of the mechanism of excitation of a set of resonant modes at the argument interaction of a system of monochromatic oscillators with different natural frequencies both with a single monochromatic external influence and among themselves.

At the same time, synchronization and adaptation of these oscillatory modes is carried out by a monochromatic influence common for all of them, the frequency of which can differ from the natural frequencies of oscillators in tens and hundreds of times.

These model representations have been applied by us, for example, for modeling and explaining the phenomena of interaction of the Sun with planets and planets of the Solar System with their own satellites, as well as for presenting an argumental model of the controlled thermonuclear reaction [24].

Continuing the logic (I) - (IV) with respect to the considered experiment with a set of argument pendulums interacting with the same electromagnetic field of a solenoid fed from a 50 Hz AC source, consider the following model.

Suppose that we have a number of oscillating systems A, B, C, D, E, ..., which are able to enter into argumental interaction with each other. The argument connectivity of any pair of them gives rise to a number of stable modes, each of which represents an individual physical object. Thus, from A and B we obtain objects $(AB)_1, (AB)_2, \dots, (AB)_n, \dots$ and so on, from C и D - objects $(CD)_1, (CD)_2, \dots, (CD)_m, \dots$ and so on. Each of these objects, as a stable oscillatory mode with certain characteristics of frequency, amplitude and phase, represents an oscillatory system which, in principle, is able to enter into argumental relatedness with other oscillatory systems. For example, the argumental coupling of $(AB)_n$ and $(CD)_m$ creates a number of individual physical objects $[(AB)_n(CD)_m]_2, \dots, [(AB)_n(CD)_m]_k$

This process can, in principle, be applied over and over again, resulting in a gigantic number of individual physical objects connected to each other in a hierarchical order. The new objects obtained at each step form the basis for the formation of the next level of objects. Due to the collective nature of the argumental binding, each of the newly formed objects maintains its individual existence and characteristic parameters, while at the same time participating in the formation and functioning (life-activity) of objects at a higher level of the hierarchy.

Naturally, the realization of such hierarchies of oscillatory modes in a particular physical system can be limited by many factors and conditions. Of which conditions of stability of functional modes at different levels of hierarchy and effects of "quantum jumps" in modes of participating systems are of special interest.

Without going into the details of a particular physical system, consider, for example, the effect of argumental linking two stable modes, e.g., $(AB)_3$ and $(CD)_5$, in order to obtain new objects of type $[(AB)_3(CD)_5]_k$. The existence of any stable mode of the coupled system $(AB)_3(CD)_5$ clearly implies that the corresponding changes in the phase, frequency, and amplitude values of the combined system must not exceed the stability boundaries of each of the participating systems $(AB)_3$ and $(CD)_5$. Changes in internal or external parameters force the system to "switch" to another stable mode (e.g. $(AB)_3 \rightarrow (AB)_1$), which will entail a chain of abrupt transitions in the functional modes of all the systems in which $(AB)_3$ participated, moving up the hierarchy. Cascades of a similar kind play an integral role in the control mechanism of many natural processes, including especially processes in living organisms.

These brief remarks serve to give some preliminary insight into the vast field of new vibrational phenomena that has opened up due to the "collectively generative" properties qualities of argumental interactions.

A special place in these phenomena is occupied by questions of the connection between oscillatory systems through a single mechanism of argumentative interaction, both between immediate neighbors and with distant systems and sources of influence. In this sense, it is appropriate to use the philosophical concept of "coherence of argumentative oscillatory systems and processes" in the sense that they are all interconnected.

2.4. Electric Argumental Oscillator [17, 85]

The electrical analog of the interactions of electromechanical oscillators with an external periodic force discussed above in this section is the device represented by the block diagram in Fig. 11 and [17] This device contains: an input circuit (alternator) 1, a control unit 2, an electric oscillating circuit 3, a phase shifter 4, a pulse shaper 5 and a launch unit 6. A more detailed description of specific electrical circuits and the results of experimental studies is given in papers [7, 17, 29]. The results of our studies have been confirmed by American and French scientists [85, 88, 92 -99].

The experiments performed on the setup, block diagram of which is shown in Fig. 11, allowed to confirm all the properties and features described in detail in the description of the argumental electromechanical systems discussed above in §§ 2.1 - 2.4. Therefore, we will not dwell on their discussion.

Figure 11
Block diagram of an electric argument oscillator

2.5. “Wave” Argumental Oscillator [18, 24 - 26, 30]

Above, we considered various options for the practical implementation of Dubochinsky's electromechanical and electrical oscillators, which are striking examples of the potential diversity of oscillatory systems in which the “external force” depends on the configuration of the system and not only on time. More natural from the point of view of theoretical physics, but much more difficult to implement in a simple mechanical model is a spatial oscillator (in this case, in the form of a body fixed on a spring), interacting with a high-frequency electromagnetic field (see Fig. 12). This scheme is discussed in detail in [1, 21]. This oscillator is very similar to the model used by Planck in his studies of blackbody radiation apart from one important difference. In Planck's study each of the atoms is considered as an “elementary oscillator”. He discovered a fundamental paradox while comparing the spectral characteristics of radiation from a completely black body, calculated on the basis of Maxwell's laws, with completely different spectral characteristics, which was obtained experimentally. To resolve this paradox, Planck made a hypothesis about the “elementary quantum of action”, which controls the energy exchange between oscillators and the radiation field. Subsequently, Planck's hypothesis of a quantum of action was confirmed by many experiments and was accepted as a universal physical principle.

Figure 12
The argumental analog of Planck's “elementary oscillator”

However, this hypothetical “elementary oscillator” was essentially the same as the “forced oscillator” described in classical physics. Moreover, the spatial orientation (position) of the oscillator is not taken into account when describing its interaction with the radiation field.

What happens if we assume that the amplitude of the oscillatory system greatly exceeds the wavelength of the field? In this case, the oscillator will be effected by the field, which alternates depending on the position of the oscillator and time.

The model under consideration represents “argumental oscillations” of a slightly different type than the basic electromechanical oscillator (see § 2.1), but which will also have a series of “quantized amplitudes”, the values of which can be calculated on the basis of the methods developed by us, which are described below.

Consider an argument-modified Planck elementary oscillator (see Fig. 12), which interacts with a monochromatic electromagnetic wave.

Let an electric charge q of mass m oscillate along the x -axis under the action of a nonlinear restoring force near some fixed point. The electromagnetic wave propagates in the x -axis direction and has a longitudinal component of the electric field E . The equation of motion of the charge interacting with the wave can be represented as:

$$m(\ddot{x} + 2\beta\dot{x} + \omega_0^2 \text{Sin}x) = Eq \text{Sin}(\nu t - kx) = \Phi(x, t), \quad (21)$$

where β is the attenuation coefficient, ω_0 is the natural frequency of small oscillations of the charge, ν is the wave frequency, k is the wave number.

Let us consider the case when $\nu > \omega_0$.

We assume that when the charge oscillations are excited by a wave, the symmetry of its motions with respect to the equilibrium position is not essentially broken, and the charge coordinate changes according to the law

$$x = a \sin \theta, \quad \theta = \omega t + \alpha, \quad a = a(t), \quad \alpha = \alpha(t). \quad (22)$$

Substituting into the right part of equation (21) the solution of (22) and decomposing the obtained expression into a Bessel series, we transform $\Phi(x, t)$ to the form:

$$\Phi(x, t) = Eq \text{Sin}(\nu t - ka \text{Sin} \theta) = Eq \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} J_n(ka) \text{Sin}(\nu t - n\theta). \quad (23)$$

Assuming that

$$\dot{x} = a\omega \cos \theta, \quad \dot{a} \sin \theta + \dot{\alpha} a \cos \theta = 0, \quad (24)$$

according to the Krylov-Bogoliubov method [39] we have in the first approximation

$$\frac{da}{dt} = -\beta a + \frac{F}{\omega} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} J_n(ka) \sin(\nu t - n\theta) \cos \theta, \quad (25)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{\omega^2 - \Omega^2}{2\omega} - \frac{F}{\omega a} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} J_n(ka) \sin(\nu t - n\theta) \sin \theta, \quad (26)$$

where Ω is the frequency of natural oscillations of the charge with amplitude a , corresponding to the solution of equation (21) at $\beta = 0$ and $E = 0$:

$$F = \frac{Eq}{m} \cdot \Omega^2 = \frac{2J_1(a)}{a} \omega_0^2 \approx \omega_0^2 \left[1 - \frac{a^2}{8} + O(a^4) \right]. \quad (27)$$

Excitation of non-damped oscillator oscillations (taking into account the simplifying assumptions adopted by us) at a frequency close to its natural frequency ω_0 is possible only if $\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} a > 1$ and as a result of the interaction of the oscillator with the wave, the force spectrum $\Phi(x, t)$ contains spectral components close enough to the frequency of its natural oscillations. Then the influence of these spectral components will sharply prevail over the rest (the so-called argumental resonance [31] will take place).

The right part of equation (21) will have the form:

$$\frac{1}{m}\Phi(x,t) \approx FJ_{\frac{\nu}{\omega}-1}(ka)\sin[\omega t - (\frac{\nu}{\omega}-1)\alpha] - FJ_{\frac{\nu}{\omega}+1}(ka)\sin[\omega t + (\frac{\nu}{\omega}+1)\alpha]. \quad (28)$$

Taking into account (28), the averaged values of the right-hand sides of equations (25) and (26) will have the form:

$$\frac{da_s}{dt} = -\beta a_s + \frac{F}{2\omega_s} [J_{s-1}(ka_s) + J_{s+1}(ka_s)] \sin(pt - \gamma_s), \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha_s}{dt} = \frac{\Omega_s^2 - \omega_s^2}{2\omega_s} - \frac{F}{2\omega_s a_s} [J_{s-1}(ka_s) + J_{s+1}(ka_s)] \cos(pt - \gamma_s), \quad (30)$$

where

$$p = \nu - \frac{\nu}{\omega_s} \ll \omega_s, \quad \gamma_s = \frac{\nu}{\omega_s} \alpha_s, \quad \omega_s = \frac{\nu}{s}. \quad (31)$$

According to the known recurrence relations for Bessel functions, equations (29) and (30) can be represented in the form:

$$\frac{da_s}{dt} = -\beta a_s + \frac{\nu F}{\omega_s^2 ka_s} J_s(ka_s) \sin(pt - \gamma_s), \quad (32)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha_s}{dt} = \frac{\Omega_s^2 - \omega_s^2}{2\omega_s} - \frac{F}{\omega_s a_s} J'_s(ka_s) \cos(pt - \gamma_s). \quad (33)$$

In the regime of stable charge oscillations, we have

$$\frac{da_s}{dt} = 0, \quad \frac{d\alpha_s}{dt} = 0. \quad (34)$$

For the regime of steady charge oscillations (34) equations (32) and (33) are transformed to the form:

$$\beta a_s = -\frac{\nu F}{\omega_s^2 ka_s} J_s(ka_s) \sin \gamma_s, \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{\Omega_s^2 - \omega_s^2}{2\omega_s} = \frac{F}{\omega_s a_s} J'_s(ka_s) \cos \gamma_s. \quad (36)$$

In accordance with the obtained results, relations (22) - (23) allow us to establish the following relation between the neighboring values of stable amplitudes of oscillations of the system and their corresponding extrema of the Bessel function [28]

$$a_i/a_{i+1} = j_{N,i} / j_{N,i+1} \quad (i = 1,2,3,\dots; \quad N = 1,2,3,\dots), \quad (37)$$

where $j_{N,i}$ is the i -th extremum (or the argument Z) of the Bessel function $J_N(Z)$ of the first kind.

This relation can be interpreted as follows:

"A vibrating system realizing argumental interactions with an external periodic wave action can only be in such a stable dynamical regime, the amplitude of oscillations a_i , which belongs to a discrete series i ($i = 1,2,3,\dots$) of potentially possible stable quantized amplitudes determined by the corresponding series of extrema of the Bessel function".

It is necessary to emphasize the fundamental difference between the "argumental-coupled approach" and the approach of many mathematicians and physicists who for years have been trying to deduce the "quantization" of microscopic systems from classical

mechanics by more or less arbitrarily introducing “nonlinear” terms into the equations of motion. Recall that the quantization of the amplitudes of the Doubochinski’s argumental oscillator is an experimentally discovered physical pattern that cannot be derived mathematically from classical mechanics. Moreover, we do not claim that the laws of radiation of a black body or the laws of quantum mechanics can be deduced from the principles set forth in this paper. We just pay attention to the analogy between a microscopic quantum and the properties of “argumental-coupled oscillations” at the macroscopic level.

2.6. Argumental model of the Solar System [23, 25].

The following factors served as the basis for applying the concept of wave argumental interactions to the study of the distribution structure of space objects (planets, planetary satellites, and other formations):

- The phenomena of commensurability and resonance in the motion structure of the Solar System - (including planets, asteroids, planetary satellites) - have been the object of detailed discussion and experimental investigation in recent years. Systematic observations and measurements have been made using all available means. A significant amount of empirical data on the solar system has been obtained from the Voyager 2 mission. The understanding of the inevitable resonant nature of evolving cosmic oscillating systems leads to a number of interesting concepts about the resonant nature of the dynamics of the motion of the Solar System:

- A number of phenomena in the structure of the solar system have been considered anomalous or incomprehensible. For example, the periods of revolution of celestial bodies vary over a relatively narrow range of values, even though their masses differ significantly. These and other phenomena do not fit within the framework of classical celestial mechanics and are actually ignored due to the lack of a traditional explanation.

- The development of cosmonautics and modern astrophysics requires: understanding the origin of anomalies; filling gaps in existing theoretical models; clarification of some phenomena, such as the nature of stability, commensurability, periodicity and resonances and their probable preference, bearing in mind that the above-mentioned phenomena are observed not only among celestial bodies, but also among artificial satellites.

- Almost all modern scientists come to the conclusion that the new picture of the Universe is based on the closing of the ring of Nature, which leads to a close relationship between the physics of the microcosm and astrophysics. General data on the structure of the near-Earth, deep space and especially the Solar System cannot be reliably interpreted without a general idea of the wave nature of the occurring phenomena [26].

- According to the concept of the wave Universe, large astronomical objects are considered as wave dynamical systems, which are in a certain sense analogous to the atomic system [26]. From this point of view, the Solar System is considered as a wave dynamical system. Its components - celestial bodies (Sun, planets, satellites and small celestial bodies) and interplanetary continuum (interplanetary plasma, electromagnetic field, etc.) are described in the context of a common dynamic substance - the field*.

In accordance with the general assumptions [7, 29, 47], we assume that the oscillating system of charges at argumental interaction with waves can be used as a general model to describe the Solar System.

The calculations performed in accordance with the above assumptions allowed us to formulate the following law: "The distances of the planets relative to the Sun are distributed as some partial values of the arguments of the Bessel function of the first kind".

The distances of the planets of the Solar System are presented in Table 5. For comparison, the data of direct astronomical measurements are given in parallel with the results of calculations performed in accordance with the classical Titius-Bode law and using the "oscillator-wave" argumental model described in detail in [29].

Table 5

Planets of the solar system	Astronomical observations of the distances of the planets from the Sun		Calculated normalized values of distances of planets from the Sun in accordance with the Titius-Bode law $a_k = 0,4 + 0,3 \times 2^k$		Calculated normalized values of the distances between the planets and the Sun according to the "oscillator-wave" argument model	
	A.E.(10 ⁶ km)	normalized values	k	a _k	i	$\frac{a_i}{a_3} = \frac{j_{8,i}}{j_{8,5}}$
Mercury	57.9	0.39	$-\infty$	0.4	1	0.392
Venus	108.2	0.72	0	0.7	3	0.723
Earth	149.6	1.00	1	1.00	5	1.000
Mars	227.9	1.52	2	1.6	9	1.530
Asteroids	415.9	2.78	3	2.8	19	2.824
Jupiter	778.3	5.20	4	5.20	38	5.201
Saturn	1427.0	9.54	5	10,0	71	9,474
Chiron	2051,0	13.71	It's impossible to calculate		104	13,689
Uranus	2869.6	19.18	6	19.6	147	19.180
Neptune	4496.6	30.06	7	38,8	232	30,035
Pluto	5934.6	39.67	8	77,2	307	39,598
Sedna	13500.0	90,24	9	154	705	90,24

* The phenomenological and dynamical description of such systems is related to mega-quantum wave dynamics. Assuming that the solar system is a wave dynamical system and, therefore, the micro-mega-analogy is valid, a number of conclusions were made on the basis of dynamical isomorphism of the structures of the atom and the solar system [51]. Different variants of quantization were used - by Bohr, De Broglie, Sommerfeld, Schrödinger and others. The essence of all these fundamental works is a substantiation of existence of megawaves realizing short-range interactions on a scale commensurable with the scale of systems in any megasystem of the Universe and, in particular, in the Solar System, representing an analogue of De Broglie waves for giant astronomical systems. At that, in general opinion, the main problem at present is more detailed identification and phenomenological and dynamical description of the megaquantum structure of the Solar System and similar systems consisting of the central body and satellites.

2.7. Argumental interpretation of the origin of Schumann waves

Let us consider a model based on the argument interpretation of the origin of Schumann waves*.

The proposed approach is based on the assumption that there is a specific argumental interaction of the spherical resonator "ionosphere-Earth" with regular wave radiations. An example of such a model of interaction in a general form was considered in [8-20, 24, 28-35, 42, 45]. The main result of the performed studies is the law of distribution of frequencies (periods) of the resonator oscillations (at argument interaction with a wave) in accordance with the distribution of extrema of the Bessel function.

Thus, with the help of calculations on the argumental model "oscillator-wave", the possible values of extrema of the Bessel function of the first kind were determined, which correspond to a number of values of frequencies of Schumun waves, presented in the second row of Table 6.

Таблица 6

Extremes Functions Bessel functions	$J_{2,2}$	$J_{2,4}$	$J_{2,6}$	$J_{2,8}$	$J_{2,10}$	$J_{2,12}$	$J_{2,14}$	$J_{2,16}$
Numerical values J_{2n}	7,367	13,883	20,247	26,512	32,880	39,180	45,476	51,769
Schumann Wave frequency values	8	14	20	26	32	39	45	50

The values of the extrema of the Bessel function of the first kind given in this Table practically coincide with the values of frequencies determined by Schumann's formulas.

* By studying electromagnetic fields in the Earth-ionosphere cavity, Schumann predicted the existence of natural resonances in the ionosphere first theoretically. His calculations, based on the size of the Earth and its ionosphere, first showed the frequency of the main resonance of the Earth-about 7.8 Hz, which is called the Schumann resonance frequency. Speaking about the resonator "Earth - ionosphere", sometimes use its analogy with a bell. Each bell is known to have its own (fundamental) frequency and a number of harmonics that give the sound a unique timbre. In order for a bell to vibrate, it is necessary to strike it or to give it a primary energy impulse, which can be applied anywhere - the bell will respond in its entirety. It is believed that this is approximately how the primary energetic rocking (pumping) of the Earth's resonator occurs. From this analogy they come to the conclusion that the resonator "Earth - ionosphere" has a certain basic frequency (7.83 Hz) and a number of harmonics - resonance frequencies. Eight frequencies of Schumann waves are known (their approximate values are 8-14-20-26-32-39-45-50 Hz).

There are several hypotheses of the origin of electromagnetic waves in the Earth-ionosphere resonator. The most widespread at present is the hypothesis that the main cause of excitation of the ionosphere at resonant frequencies is discharges of atmospheric electricity - lightning. The next stage of development of this direction of researches is connected with the German doctor Herbert Konig (Herbert Konig), who in 1953 has paid attention to coincidence of the main resonance frequency of ionosphere 7,83 Hz with a range of alpha waves (7,5-13 Hz) of human brain. So the hypothesis about coincidence of frequencies of Shumun waves with frequencies of the majority of main rhythms of human brain was confirmed.

At the same time, the question of regularity (periodicity) of discharges and the possibility of realization of stable oscillations of the Earth-ionosphere resonator by random (irregular) influences, for example, thunderstorm discharges, remained open.

It should also be noted that some provisions of modern theoretical ideas about the origin of Schumann waves and frequency-energy pumping of the resonator "ionosphere-Earth" are difficult to recognize, in the opinion of some researchers, as correct or reliable.

Thus ...

It can be stated that we [1-34, 40 - 43] have experimentally established for the first time the existence of quantum and discreteness properties realized at interaction of an external monochromatic force with macroscopic oscillators represented by nonlinear or quasi-linear oscillatory systems, whose motion is fully described by the laws of classical mechanics.

3. Argumental resonance [31]

3.1 Modern concepts *

The main conclusions, following from the review of classical ideas about resonance phenomena, are :

- the concept of resonance refers exclusively to oscillatory (periodic, cyclic) processes and systems;
- resonance is considered as a result of forcing (perturbation) of oscillations by an external force;
- at least two systems or two processes are involved in the realization of this phenomenon;
- there is no and cannot be an out-of-system realization of resonance;
- The most common is the following formulation of resonance (taken, for example, from the physical encyclopedia): a frequency-selective response of an oscillating system to a periodic external influence, in which there is a sharp increase in the amplitude of stationary oscillations. It is observed when the frequency of the external influence approaches certain values characteristic of a given system. In linear oscillating systems, the number of such resonance frequencies corresponds to the number of degrees of freedom and they coincide with the frequencies of natural oscillations. In nonlinear oscillating systems, whose reactive and dissipative parameters depend on the magnitude of the external influence, resonance can manifest itself as a response to an external force influence, and as a reaction to a periodic change in the parameters*. In its strict meaning, the term "resonance" refers only to the case of force action.

Argument oscillations (and the Macrophysical Quantum Effect) completely change the ideas about the mechanism of resonance phenomena.

* Classical notions about resonance (both in classical and quantum mechanics) are connected with equality or closeness to each other of natural frequencies of systems entering into mutual relations. Sometimes problems when one of the systems contains a harmonic at the frequency of the other system are considered.

The concept of resonance is also associated with the efficiency of energy conversion, which is close to 100% when the frequencies of these systems are equal (or close).

Sometimes it is possible to meet hypotheses related to the explanation of the nature of absorption or reflection of waves by matter, based on the use of the phenomenon of resonance. In these cases (as claimed by a number of researchers) the absorption of wave energy by matter occurs predominantly at resonance. Otherwise, when the natural frequencies of waves and matter differ from each other, absorption of wave energy by matter does not occur and matter is considered transparent to non-resonant wave frequencies.

In some new theories, the resonance phenomena of wave absorption by matter are associated not with the structure of the atoms of matter itself, but with resonance (or non-resonance) phenomena of excitation of bonds between the constituents, for example, of an atom. In these cases, it is said that in the absence of resonance between the frequencies of waves and frequencies of bonds of the constituents of a substance atom, there is no interaction and the substance is transparent to such radiations.

As it was shown above (see Section 2), resonance excitation of an oscillator by a wave or a concentrated periodic force (irrespective of the form of this force) can occur when frequencies of the oscillator and the periodic influence differ from each other in tens and hundreds times and the influence itself is monochromatic.

Thus, argumental resonance is not limited by the equality or proximity of frequencies of the objects involved in the interaction (oscillators, waves, fields, periodic processes and forces). At argumental interactions [31] there is a self-regulated process of activation of connections, which does not depend on the ratio of natural frequencies of objects (systems, processes) participating in the interaction.

The mechanism of realization of the argument resonance is caused by the process of frequency-phase modulation* of a periodic influence (for example, a wave) by an oscillator, as a result of which in the spectrum of the promoted signal one of the spectral components is equal to (or very close to) the natural frequency of the modulating system (see relations (1), (13) - (16) and Figure 6).

The discovered phenomenon of argument resonance, which utilizes the phenomenon of argument (frequency-phase) modulation, is a fundamental feature of the processes of interaction of objects under study, accompanied by autoregulation of energy exchange.

Such possibilities of resonant (i.e., highly effective) interaction of systems have never been assumed and considered (and realized) before.

3.2. Multiple resonance *[54]

Another important feature of argumental oscillations is the possibility of realization of multiple argument resonance. The physical meaning of this phenomenon is that argumental oscillations can be realized by several oscillators with identical or different natural frequencies as a result of interaction with the same periodic influence of a monochromatic frequency. Such an example was considered in § 2.4 for the case of the interaction of four mechanical pendulums with the field of the same electromagnet.

Multiple argumental resonance allows us to explain how one and the same monochromatic radiation can represent the "mother" origin of existence and generation of complex vibrational objects such as cosmic formations like the solar system (see § 2.7) and other macro-structures.

* The current situation in physics is due to the fact that, as 100 years ago, it is rarely possible to find exact solutions of nonlinear equations in explicit analytical form. Therefore, a rich arsenal of approximate or asymptotic methods has been developed in the theory of oscillations. Common to all these methods is that the initial equation (see, for example, equations (1) or (9)) is linearized, reduced to a "universal" form, and then the construction of an approximate solution of the simplified equation is carried out. In this way, a transition is made to the study of the linear equation describing the excitation of a linear oscillator by an external influence; at the same time, a term representing the response to the external influence is introduced into this equation (by means of a number of assumptions).

As for the equation thus obtained, the external influence (represented by the above-mentioned response) has a frequency equal to the frequency of natural oscillations of the oscillator. As it is known from the theory of linear oscillations, in this case resonance occurs, which is expressed in an unlimited increase in the amplitude of oscillations according to a linear law.

3.3. Physical mechanism of argumental multi-resonant interaction.

The basic principles of argumental interactions can be best understood when the case with an argument pendulum (see § 2 and [20 -32] is investigated using two different but complementary idealizations. The first one demonstrates most simply the phase-dependent nature of argument interactions and the genesis of "quantized amplitudes"; the second one allows to understand the mechanism of resonance energy transfer between systems with very different frequencies.

Suppose that the magnetic field of the solenoid is practically homogeneous within a certain narrow interaction zone located near the vertical equilibrium position of the pendulum, and becomes zero outside this zone (see § 2.1.1 - Figure 4). In this case, the interaction of the pendulum with the alternating magnetic field can be described quite simply in the following way. For small initial amplitudes, when the pendulum remains inside the "interaction zone" with the electromagnet field, the external force acting on the pendulum is practically independent of its position and can be represented as follows

$$F = A \cos(\nu t),$$

where ν is the frequency of the alternating current supplying the solenoid.

Here we have the classical case of excitation of forced oscillations of a pendulum by an external periodic force. At a large difference between the frequency ν of the influencing force and the natural frequency of the pendulum, the classical analysis shows that the pendulum's movements at the natural frequency will be suppressed, leaving only its oscillations around the equilibrium position at the frequency of the external field, which is confirmed by experimental data.

A completely different situation occurs when the initial motion of the pendulum is large enough to take it outside the "interaction zone".

In this case, the external force acting on the pendulum can be represented in the following form:

$$F = F(x, t) = \varepsilon(x) A \cos(\nu t),$$

where x is the angular deflection of the pendulum and $\varepsilon(x)$ is a function defined as follows: $\varepsilon(x)=1$ when $-x_0 > x < x_0$ (the pendulum is in the interaction zone) and $\varepsilon(x)=0$ (the pendulum is outside the interaction zone).

* The term "multiple resonance" first appears in the works of Saracen and de la Riva [104 - 107], begun in 1889 and devoted to the study of wave propagation through wires. The purpose of these studies was to repeat and confirm Hertz's observations about the existence and propagation with finite speed of electromagnetic waves in a wire. In doing so, an explanation of this phenomenon was proposed, according to which a generator emits "all possible wavelengths within certain limits and therefore creates a continuous spectrum." Thus, under the influence of the same primary oscillator, each of the (multiple) resonators responds essentially to only one of these frequencies specific to it. This phenomenon, called multiple resonance by Saracen and de la Rive, was not yet well understood at the time. Henri Poincaré (1854-1912) and Wilhelm Bjerknes (1862-1951), Hertz's assistant, proposed various explanations based on the large difference existing between the attenuation of the oscillator and the resonator. This line of research was not further developed,

Here it is important to emphasize that the phenomenon of Duboshinsky's multiple resonance, considered in the present paper, has no relation to the studies of Saracen and de la Riva: our studies consider the phenomenon arising from the argument interaction [8, 24, 34, 53] of two oscillating systems with different monochromatic frequencies that do not contain any harmonics (or fascicles) before the interaction.

Now let us consider the motion of the pendulum between successive passages of its points of maximum deviation from the equilibrium position (when the pendulum velocity is zero). In each of these half-periods, the pendulum first moves in free motion from its maximum to the point where it enters the interaction zone. Then, passing through the interaction zone, the pendulum is affected by alternately accelerating and decelerating pulses. The total contributions or energy losses of the pendulum as a result of its passage through the interaction zone depends on the phases of the solenoid current at the moments of its entry and exit from this zone. If the number of accelerating and decelerating half-periods of the electromagnet field is equal during the pendulum's passage through the interaction zone, the integral contribution of the field energy to the pendulum's oscillations is zero. If the pendulum leaves the interaction zone integrating a non-fold number of periods of the electromagnet field, the pendulum will experience a nonzero integral contribution of the field energy, which will be equivalent to a nonzero acceleration or deceleration of the pendulum [39]. Then, leaving the interaction zone, the pendulum in its free motion rises to a new maximum height (in the general case, different from the previous one) and then performs a new half-cycle of oscillations.

It is easy to see that the functional relations between phases and amplitudes for successive half-periods are rather complicated and the attempt to characterize the long-term behavior of the system in the general case faces enormous difficulties. However, if we focus attention on the special case of quasi-stable regimes, whose existence is known from experiments with real argument pendulums, a direct analysis is possible.

Let us assume, for simplicity, that for quasi-steady modes the amplitude of the pendulum oscillations is unchanged. Then the energy exchange between the pendulum and the field of the electromagnet will be determined only by phase relations. In this case, the stability of the modes will be determined by the type of functional dependence of the energy contribution on the phase of the pendulum entry into the interaction zone

In spite of the fact that this method is rather labor-intensive, it is possible to show the existence of quasi-stable modes of the argument pendulum. However, this approach has an essential disadvantage that it cannot be easily extended to many other systems (see Section 2) in which the macrophysical "quantum" effect can be demonstrated. This drawback is eliminated by the second method, which is presented below.

Let us consider the necessary conditions for the realization of the stable mode of oscillation of an oscillator with a number of discrete amplitudes.

In the stable mode of oscillation, the pendulum must "enter" the interaction zone every half-period so that the solenoid field puts into its motion the same portion of energy as in the previous half-period, taking into account that the direction of motion of the pendulum is reversed every half-period. This means that the phase of the alternating current in the solenoid must be strictly opposite to the phase of the preceding moment of input. Thus, the time between successive inputs to the interaction zone must take the following form $(m + (m + \frac{1}{2})\tau$, where $\tau = 1/\nu$ is the period of current in the solenoid, and m is an integer. For the total period T of the pendulum oscillation we obtain the relation $T = (2m + 1)\tau$. So, the possible periods of stable modes of the argument pendulum are included in a certain discrete series.

The corresponding series of amplitudes can be calculated using the classical formulas for the relationship between the amplitude and period of the pendulum, assuming that this non-isochronous dependence is practically unchanged as a result of the interaction of the pendulum with the magnetic field of the coil. The calculated values of discrete amplitudes obtained in this way are in agreement with those quasi-steady modes observed in experiments [7].

In accordance with the above considerations, one can come to the conclusion that quantization of pendulum amplitudes depends on its nonlinearity and nonisochronism. Nevertheless, it is experimentally established that quantization of amplitudes is preserved (though with different numerical values) when instead of a nonisochronous physical pendulum a quasilinear mechanical oscillator is used (as, for example, a balance system of electric clocks considered in [18, 84]), whose nonisochronality is extremely small. In this case, quantization of amplitudes is connected with changes of transit time of passage (passage) of the pendulum magnet through the zone of interaction with the solenoid electromagnetic field.

Now let us turn to the second method of investigation of the argument pendulum, which applies much more widely and indeed leads to the creation of a general theory of argument interactions. The second method begins with the idea of describing the interaction of the pendulum with the solenoid field in terms of the phase-frequency-amplitude modulation of its initial free motion.

For this purpose, it is useful to abstract from the specific properties of the pendulum and consider an arbitrary linear or nonlinear mechanical oscillator with one degree of freedom, which can realize a continuous set of possible periodic motions depending on the initial conditions, each of which is associated with an appropriate amplitude, frequency, and phase. Choosing a suitable generalized coordinate x for the oscillator, we represent this set of periodic motions using the function $x = x(A, \omega, \phi, t)$ such that to each set of values (A, ω, ϕ) , x corresponds a periodic function t with frequency ω , amplitude A and phase ϕ .

We assume further that this function represents the "free" motion of the mechanical oscillator. Let us consider the case when the mechanical oscillator interacts with a periodic, spatially inhomogeneous field whose frequency may be many (e.g., orders of magnitude) higher than the frequency of the mechanical oscillator. The effect of the field on the motion of the mechanical oscillator can be described by the following differential equation:

$$\ddot{x} + 2\beta\dot{x} + g(x) = F(x)\cos(\nu t). \quad (38)$$

This notation contains, in the special case, the equation of the argumental pendulum when $g(x) = \omega_0^2 \sin x$. $F(x)$ is the function that was defined above as $\varepsilon(x)$, and β is the dissipation factor of the energy of the pendulum (see § 2.1.2, formula (4')). In fact, the macroscopic effect of quantization of amplitudes does not itself depend strongly on the features of the function expressing the spatial dependence of the field action. The shape of the function determines the numerical values of the "quantized" amplitudes.

Suppose that essential characteristics of the mechanical oscillator do not change very much due to interaction with the field, so that its motion can be approximated closely enough by a "free motion" $x = x(A, \omega, \phi, t)$, where parameters A, ω, ϕ are no longer strictly constant and can slowly fluctuate in time around certain averaged values.

Turning to the right-hand side of equation (38), we can see how the mechanical oscillations of the pendulum "modulate" the external force in such a way that new spectral components of the influencing field arise. For any fixed values of A, ω and ϕ the function $F(x)$ is a periodic function of time t , which can be represented by a Fourier series whose coefficients are functions of A, ω and ϕ .

Let us represent the right part of equation (38) in the form:

$$F(x(A, \omega, \phi, t)) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n(A, \omega, \phi) e^{in\omega t} \quad (39)$$

Let us transform the right part of equation (39):

$$\begin{aligned} \cos(\nu t) \times \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n(A, \omega, \phi) e^{in\omega t} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n(A, \omega, \phi) e^{in\omega} (e^{i\nu t} + e^{-i\nu t}) = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n(A, \omega, \phi) e^{i(n\omega + \nu)t} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_n(A, \omega, \phi) e^{i(n\omega - \nu)t}. \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

"The force" on the right side of equation (39) contains the frequency components $n\omega + \nu$ and $n\omega - \nu$, where n can be zero or any positive or negative integer. No matter how large ν Таким образом, движение осциллятора в поле высокочастотной силы приводит к появлению в спектре этой силы компоненты, частота которой совпадает с собственной частотой осциллятора. Это открывает возможность резонансного вклада энергии высокочастотного поля в колебания низкочастотного осциллятора []. Именно это и происходит в устойчивых режимах колебаний аргументального маятника и подобных систем. may be compared to ω , this spectrum will contain components of the same order as ω . Of particular interest is the case where ν is an integer multiple of ω . If, for example, $\nu = N\omega$, it is easy to see that (40) will contain two terms whose frequency is exactly equal to ω , namely for $n = 1 - N$ and $n = N + 1$. Taken together these two terms give the following frequency component ω :

$$[C_{1-N}(A, \omega, \phi) + C_{N+1}(A, \omega, \phi)] e^{i\omega t}. \quad (41)$$

Thus, the motion of the oscillator in the field of a high-frequency force leads to the appearance of a component in the spectrum of this force, the frequency of which coincides with the natural frequency of the oscillator. This opens up the possibility of the resonant contribution of the high-frequency field energy to the oscillations of the low-frequency oscillator [27, 29]. This is exactly what happens in stable modes of oscillations of the argumental pendulum and similar systems.

It is important to note that the low-frequency component was not initially present in this field, but was created by interaction of the field with the mechanical oscillator in a way

similar to frequency-phase modulation in radio engineering. Self-organization of the resonant energy contribution through generation and selection of additional frequency spectral components is a characteristic feature of argument interactions. It can be said that systems by mutual modulation create a specific channel and find a "common language" for their communication.

In order to proceed to quantitative evaluations after the above qualitative analysis, it is necessary to compare both parts of equation (38), focusing on fluctuations in the values of A , ω and ϕ , which are responsible for the regulation that ensures the emergence and maintenance of stable oscillatory modes of the oscillator. The analysis leads to complex equations involving functions, which, as a result of applying the Krylov-Bogoliubov-Mitropolsky averaging method [39], allow us to conclude that there exist quasi-stable modes corresponding to a discrete series of averaged values of A , ω and ϕ .

The fundamentals of the theory of argument oscillations were developed in 1970-1980 [6, 18,], which made it possible to model most of the properties of argument oscillations and to show good quantitative agreement with experimental and numerical data. Practical algorithms for calculations of quantized amplitude values for mechanical and radio oscillators realizing the argumental mechanism of interaction were also created.

It should be noted that these studies have established a close connection between argumental coupling and the solution of a certain type of differential equations with a deviating argument [9 - 13].

3.4 General provisions of argumental resonance

Argumental processes are characterized by the fact that the excitatory influence does not directly transfer energy to the system, but influences it through the argument of the function that describes the force or momentum.

Such interaction forms a fundamentally different scheme of energy exchange based on phase matching of frequencies and phases, leading to stable oscillatory modes with quantum-like structure.

The main feature of argumental resonances is that stability and discreteness of oscillatory states do not require "rigid" energy transfer, as in classical systems, but are realized by matching the information parameters of the external signal with the intrinsic dynamics of the system.

Argument oscillations provide a peculiar energy balance, in which the system selects such modes where the energy exchange with the external field is optimal and the phase matching is maximized.

This makes it possible to realize oscillatory processes with surprisingly high stability in amplitude and frequency at small excitation powers.

Such feature brings argument oscillations closer to the phenomena of coherence in quantum systems and explains the phenomenon of quantization of amplitudes in macroscopic objects.

The key element of the argument interaction is the mechanism of autotuning of the phase of oscillations of the excitation signal. The oscillator is able to "adjust" to the frequency of external influence due to nonlinear feedback, which leads to phase capture and the appearance of stable discrete states.

This synchronization effect provides the formation of spatiotemporal structures that are stable to variations of external excitation and dissipative properties of oscillators and manifests itself in quantization of its amplitudes.

Stationary states of macroscopic oscillators can be considered as stable resonance configurations arising at fulfillment of the condition of multiple resonance

$$n\nu = m\omega_0, \quad n, m \in Z, \quad (42)$$

where ν is the excitation frequency, ω_0 is the natural frequency of the oscillator, n and m are integers.

This condition leads to the formation of a kind of resonance lattice, inside which only certain values of the oscillator amplitudes and energy levels are stable. Thus, the mechanism of the macroscopic quantization similar to the quantized levels in the microcosm is realized.

4. Conclusion and philosophical aspects

4.1 Results and discussion

Realized experimental and theoretical studies have shown [7] that argumental vibrational systems demonstrate a fundamentally new form of stable quantization of amplitudes at the macroscopic level. In contrast to classical systems with continuous amplitude variation depending on the excitation parameters, here we observe a strictly discrete set of stable amplitudes depending only on the initial conditions.

Such multi-stability is explained not by traditional bifurcations, but by the specificity of the argumental interaction, in which the oscillatory system itself modulates the excitation effect by selecting the spectral component closest to its own frequency. As a result, a steady consumption of energy of external periodic influence (field, wave or concentrated force) in certain portions is formed, which leads to the appearance of quantized modes of oscillators and their amplitude levels.

In a number of experiments with pendulum systems, electromagnetic resonators and electric circuits it has been demonstrated that:

- stable modes are weakly sensitive to changes in the excitation signal amplitude and the quality factor of the oscillator;
- the system is capable of switching to other discrete amplitude levels under external short-term pulse perturbations, similar to quantum jumps;
- these levels persist for a long time under sufficiently unstable external conditions.

These results show that the phenomenon of argumental resonance and argumental self-organization is reproduced in a wide range of systems - from the simplest mechanical pendulums to complex electronic structures.

We have theoretically and experimentally substantiated a new type of resonance - argumental resonance.

Traditionally, two main types of resonance phenomena are distinguished in nonlinear systems: forced resonance, when the frequencies of the oscillator and the external harmonic influence coincide; parametric resonance, when the parameters of the oscillating system (e.g., its capacitance) change in time, which can lead, under certain conditions, to an increase in amplitude.

Argumental resonance differs from both in that the oscillator is not forced to react to an external influence, but actively influences it by modulating its phase and frequency due to its own dynamics.

Thus, the external influence is not rigidly set, but "participates" in a joint energy exchange cycle with the oscillator, where the oscillatory system acts as a kind of spectral filter, selecting the most suitable excitation components. This process leads to a stable harmonization of phases and frequencies, which makes possible the formation of discrete stable amplitude modes underlying the macrophysical quantum effect.

This mechanism opens fundamentally new ways to control the modes of self-regulating systems and can be considered as a universal principle of self-organization in oscillatory processes.

The following classification of argumental resonances seems appropriate:

- argumental multiple resonance (see §§ 3.2 and 3.3);
- argumental spatial resonance at wave interactions (see § 2.6);
- stochastic (chaotic) argumental resonance (see § 2.3 and [72]);

Stochastic argumental resonance is realized in systems with two or more degrees of freedom, in the presence of random or quasi-random fluctuations. It is possible to form quasiperiodic ordered states from chaotic modes due to argumental selection. Such an effect has been confirmed in mechanical (e.g., elastic) pendulums and in models with multidimensional degrees of freedom.

The steady states of macroscopic oscillators considered in the present study can be interpreted as a result of the formation of stable resonance configurations in nonlinear systems with spatially dependent excitation. In this case, the system (for example, an oscillator interacting with a wave) finds stationary solutions satisfying the condition of multiple resonance (42), which describes a resonance lattice with possible stable vibrational states to which discrete levels of amplitude and energy correspond.

Thus, the multiple resonance plays the role of a universal mechanism generating quantum-like discreteness in macroscopic systems, where the external excitation is synchronized in phase and frequency with the intrinsic dynamics of the oscillator.

Argument systems have a unique energy-balancing mechanism: the excitation phase is matched so that optimal energy storage with minimal losses is achieved. This provides high stability and low sensitivity to changes in the amplitude of the external influence due to its phase-frequency feedback to the oscillator. Such a process can be defined as a mechanism of argumental self-organization.

Unlike classical models of self-organization based on dissipative structures (Prigogine) or principles of synergetics (Haken), argument self-organization assumes that the source of ordering is located not only inside the system, but also in a specific "information" exchange with external excitation. In this exchange, the system actively shapes the energetic response of the external force, creating the conditions for its own stability.

The key features of argumental self-organization are:

- the existence of phase-frequency feedback;
- the ability to select "resonant" components from the excitation spectrum;
- formation of discrete stable modes;
- high stability to external perturbations.

Argumental self-organization is a dynamic matching of internal parameters of an oscillator with parameters of an external periodic influence, resulting in a stable set of discrete states analogous to quantum levels but realized in classical macroscopic systems.

A distinctive feature of argumental self-organization is that the system does not simply react to the excitation, but actively shapes its spectrum and phase structure, thus creating a joint stabilization mechanism.

Thus, argumental self-organization represents a new class of self-organizing processes, where the matching of parameters of internal dynamics and external field occurs mutually and dynamically, rather than being imposed from the outside. This makes argumental systems promising for understanding stability processes at very different scales - from macroscopic mechanical oscillators to astrophysical and biological systems.

These ideas open the prospects of creating new theoretical models that integrate argumental processes with modern concepts of self-organizing systems, and allow us to offer a holistic view of the processes of stability and coordination in the Universe.

The Literature provides [72 - 103] independent confirmations of the main properties and features of the argumental oscillations based on research works carried out in university and research centers of many countries, training and educational materials, as well as on modern applied research.

These studies demonstrate the wide international interest and reproducibility of argumental oscillations and the Douboshinski's Macroscopic Quantum Effect (MQED).

4.2 Perspectives.

Modern quantum theory, when considering phenomena such as quantum entanglement, assumes a global interconnectedness of all particles and systems in the Universe, often without a satisfactory explanation of the physical mechanism of this interconnectedness. Such a view often gives rise to philosophical controversy beyond the possibilities of scientific confirmation.

The argumental theory of interactions proposed in this paper extends these ideas by relying on the principle of phase-frequency feedback, which can naturally realize the "universal" coherence of the elements of the Universe through interaction with a single controlling

origin (field, wave, radiation). As a candidate for such a universal beginning can be considered, for example, cosmic relic radiation permeating the whole space.

If we recognize that any system - from elementary particles to galactic structures - is able to enter into argumental interaction with this radiation, a natural mechanism of formation of coherent, coordinated states without recourse to "superconnected" and uncontrolled processes appears.

Proceeding from the above hypothesis, we formulated the Principle of complete closure of argumental relations in the form of the theorem "on the completeness of inverse argumental connections":

Any system possessing stable oscillatory modes, in the presence of a universal excitation field (radiation) providing phase-frequency matching, is able to enter the argument binding, closing the full loop of feedbacks between all elements participating in this interaction, and thus to reach the coordinated state without direct interaction between all participants.

Thus, the control radiation plays the role of a single argumental mediator that does not require fantastic "instantaneous" entanglement or superluminal signals.

The argumental theory proposed in this paper extends these ideas by relying on the principle of phase-frequency feedback, which can naturally realize the universal coherence of the elements of the Universe through simultaneous interaction with a single control field (radiation).

Within the framework of the argument model of the Universe [8, 14, 28, 32, 47] we can develop a formal proof of the theorem "on completeness of feedbacks". In a preliminary form it looks as follows:

- Any stable oscillatory system can be characterized by a state function with phase-frequency parameters.
- If there exists a universal field (e.g., relic radiation) capable of transmitting phase-frequency signals, then all such oscillating systems will in principle be able to tune their modes of interaction through this field.
- In the presence of a continuous spectrum of vibrational frequencies and phase exchange channels, the universal field provides a complete feedback loop simultaneously for all systems interfacing with it.
- Thus, argumental mutual coherence is a consequence not of direct interaction between all elements, but of their joint alignment with the universal control field.

Illustrations and examples:

- Argumental pendulum: interaction of a single pendulum with an alternating field source (see § 2.1.1, Figure 4);
- Group of pendulums: multiple oscillators synchronizing through the same field (see § 2.4. Fig. 10);
- Planetary orbits: stable orbital arrangements due to argumental resonance effects (see § 2.7, Table 5);

4.2.1 Possible consequences:

- the need for the obscure "instantaneous quantum entanglement" is removed;
- the possibility of unified physical principles of self-organization is confirmed;
- the classical and macrophysical quantum nature of the Universe is united;
- the foundations of universal argumental cosmology are laid, where the Universe is governed by a unified mechanism of phase-frequency matching.

4.2.2 Prospects of experimental verification:

- creation of multi-oscillatory macromodels with a single control oscillator;
- investigations of behavior of groups of pendulums or electronic oscillators synchronized by one field;
- search for analogies in the interactions of plasma and relic radiation;

This approach opens the possibility to comprehend the Universe as a single argumental system, where the role of a universal coordinating "beginning" is played, for example, by the cosmic background radiation. Thus, the phenomenon of apparent global interconnectedness (as it is described by quantum entanglement theory) receives an understandable physical explanation based on the real principles of phase-frequency interaction.

The appearance of stable discrete argumental levels gives a basis to introduce an analog of Planck's constant for macroscopic systems:

$$E_n = nh_{eff}\nu,$$

where h_{eff} — is the effective macroquantum constant determined by the excitation parameters and properties of the oscillator.

Such analogy emphasizes the single principle of quantization, manifested both in the microcosm and in the macroscale.

In terms of standing waves the stationary discrete states of the oscillator can be interpreted as spatiotemporal standing waves stabilized by phase synchronization with the excitation signal. This leads to spatially discrete energy localization similar to standing waves in atoms or resonators.

A similar approach was taken in the paper "A Hypothetical Model of the Argumental Atom" [52], where discrete energy levels are considered as the result of stable spatiotemporal resonances in the Coulomb field. This model shows agreement with the observed spectra of hydrogen-like atoms and indicates the potential of the MQED as a basis for a unified quantum and classical theory.

Thus, the argumental approach shows that discreteness is not exclusively a quantum phenomenon of the microcosm, but can be a consequence of universal nonlinear resonance mechanisms of self-organization acting at any scales. This eliminates the rigid distinction between classical and quantum physics and suggests a unified paradigm where quantization is considered as a manifestation of organized dynamics.

4.2.3 The special role of Bessel functions.

One of the key differences between the argumental theory of oscillations and classical approaches is the use of a new mathematical toolkit - the expansion of excitation functionals into series based on Bessel functions rather than on standard Fourier or Taylor coefficients.

Such a method becomes necessary when analyzing systems in which the argument of the excitation force contains complex phase-dependent structures, for example, a sinusoidal function from an oscillatory displacement of the "sine of sine" type, which is fundamentally unusual for the classical theory of oscillations. In this case, solving the problem requires taking into account the spatial and temporal structure of the excitation and its phase dependence on the system dynamics itself.

Bessel function series allow us to describe naturally the spectrum of harmonics arising from such nonlinear interaction and make it possible to identify stable modes without traditional linearization of differential equations. In fact, it is through the use of Bessel functions that it becomes possible to solve "head-on" complex nonlinear differential equations with argumental excitation, which fundamentally distinguishes the argumental approach from classical methods based on reduction and verbal stipulations of nonlinearity.

This mathematical apparatus opens a way to a full analytical description of argumental resonances and macroscopic quantization, thus eliminating a gap between classical dynamics and observable discrete states in macroscopic systems. It can be argued that Bessel functions play the role of a kind of dimensionless normalizing origin of argument interaction, determining the topology and stability of standing space-time waves and structures.

CONCLUSION - philosophical aspect

Modern science is approaching the limit of reductionist methods, where the Universe is considered as a sum of elementary constituents. The Macroscopic Quantum Effect Doubochinski's (MCED) suggests that Nature can be organized through stable collective states that are not reducible to a set of individual elements.

Argumental physics argues that these collective states are formed through resonant processes with argumental capture of phases and frequencies of an external periodic influence, which makes the harmonization of elements possible without classical coercion or rigid ties. Such a concept allows to explain many phenomena - from macroscopic standing waves to synchronization in biological and social systems as a manifestation of the universal argumental mechanism of coordination.

These considerations can be extended with the help of the Theorem on completeness of feedbacks in systems realizing argumental interactions, where any stable formation in Nature exists due to continuous coordination carried out by a single controlling field, such as, for example, relic radiation.

Thus, physical reality can be considered as a hierarchy of resonant structures interacting according to argumental laws, and not just as a set of its components. This opens up the prospect of rethinking many provisions of natural science and bringing closer the integration of physics, biology and information sciences.

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